

Perception on Virtual Marketing

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Abstract

The term Marketing intends to mainly satisfy the organisations goals and objectivities, the purpose is to anticipate their potential consumer's needs. But in today's scenario many organisations are into virtual marketing. The word "Virtual Marketing" means making use of online advertisement and some of the common platforms such as email marketing, social media marketing, display advertising and blogs etc. Virtual marketing serves as a complete contrast towards the traditional methods of advertising such as printing and broadcasting. This study concentrates on what way the customers use virtual marketing and what would be the drawbacks found in the virtual marketing. To achieve this purpose, questionnaires have been used to gather the primary data from the respondents using random sampling technique. Total number of responses collected was 76. The paper concludes by providing suggestions and measures to overcome the drawbacks in virtual marketing

Keywords: customer's satisfaction, common platforms, drawbacks, traditional marketing.

Introduction

The word "Virtual" means almost or nearly described, but not physically existing as such but made by software to appear to do so. Wherein the term "Marketing" is basically used to create, keep and satisfy the customers. According to the perspective of sales process, marketing is well-defined as processes that are interconnected and interdependent with other functions of business which are aimed at achieving customer satisfaction and interest. In Today's scenario many businesses intend to attract customers through new means of techniques such as "Virtual Marketing" by making use of latest technology and by creating the impression on the products hence this way the businesses targets the customers to purchase their products as there is a wide scope of social networking. Where as in traditional methods of marketing the customers were enforced to touch and feel the product and even the promotion of the products were restricted to certain locality or regions as newspaper advertisements, pamphlets were only means of advertising their products.

Literature Review

Udo Gottlieb, Constanza Bianchi, *Electronic Commerce Research and Application* 21, (2017) study on how Scant empirical research has examined exhibitors' experiences of participating in virtual

trade shows. This study aims to expand the understanding of the main drivers and challenges of participating in the virtual trade shows and virtual marketing capabilities required for exhibiting organisations. The research mainly depends on the technological development and strategic firm processes for exhibitors and visitors.

Dr Tariq Jalees, Huma Tariq, Syed Imran Zaman, Syed Hasnain Alam Kazmi (2014) conducted a research on social media usage in the world and especially in Pakistan has a high growth due to which it has a potential of becoming an effective marketing tool. Despite its comparatively low cost and significance, marketers are not effectively utilizing the social media. Thus this study aims to measure the effects of social variables.

Alessandra Marasco, Piera Buonincontri, Mthilda van Niekerk, Marissa Orłowski, Fevzi, (2018) conducted a research aiming to investigate the impact of virtual reality experiences created with the newest generation of wearable devices on the intention to visit sites. The study resulted that PVA of virtual reality experience with wearable devices has a positive and significant effect on behavioural intentions towards the site featured in virtual experiences.

Research Gap

Many studies have been conducted its pros and cons in virtual marketing. From the above literature review its evident that the research has been undertaken according to business perspectives and how the computer-generated today impacts the pupil's emotions, behaviours etc and to what extent the social networking is becoming one of the major tools of marketing.

Statement of the Problem

Before adoption of virtual marketing the customers were not aware of the new products into the market as it was restricted to certain local markets and the customers were enforced to visit stores physically to purchase the products. It's because the business was lacking to the reach the customer's needs and wants.

“Do customers prefer Traditional marketing or Virtual Marketing”.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to know the perceptiveness of the customers towards the collaboration of virtual marketing over traditional marketing. Keeping this in view, the following secondary objectives have been set up:

- To examine whether customers prefer traditional marketing over virtual marketing.
- The drawbacks customers face in virtual marketing.
- To give suggestions to overcome the drawbacks faced in virtual marketing.

Scope of the Study

The study was undertaken to assess the perception of various customers whether they prefer virtual marketing of different age groups. And the study also examines whether customers are satisfied with the products purchased over virtual marketing. For this purpose, respondents were selected from Bengaluru city.

Limitations of the Study

The study on “VIRTUAL MARKETING” has few limitations:

- The study is exclusively based on the primary data with the limited sample size.
- The study is constrained only on the customers' perception. The study is restricted to Bengaluru city covering different levels of age groups.

Research Methodology

The research used was simple random sampling. The primary data was collected through an online survey. The survey was carried through structured questionnaire, self-administered process. And the secondary data is collected from various articles, research papers and journals.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Number of Respondents

From the above chart 1 it is observed that 78.2% were the respondents from the age group of 18-28, 12.6% from 29-38 and other 9.2% are above the age of 39.

2. How Often Does Customer Use Social Networking?

From the chart 2 it is inferred that 81.6% use social networking daily, 3.5% use once a week, nil for twice a week, 2.3% one month and 12.6% use whenever it is required. This shows that majority of youngsters use social networking everyday as it would be because of the customer's time constraints or their interest.

3. Do Customers Often Get Affected by Negative Comments?

Chart: 3

As per in chart 3, 47.1% of customers get affected by negative comments, 16.1% say no, 36.8% are affected to some extent. This could be due to the quality issues upon the product and the customers after reviewing comments they might have the wrong impact on customers buying perception.

4. Are the Customers Satisfied with the Quality of the Product Purchased Using Virtual Marketing

Chart: 4

The above chart 4 predicts if customer is satisfied with the products or not. 20.7% are satisfied, 14.9% are not satisfied and 64.4% are satisfied to some extent. Thus, it is convinced that majority of customers use virtual marketing and it developing as per the changing trends.

Findings

It was found that majority of the population in Bengaluru city make use of technology massively, therefore there are chances of targeting the customers attention. There is an ease of purchasing products on virtual marketing. Virtual marketing saves the time of the customers. Every now and then the quality of the product differs. And few products would be manipulated with duplicate products. There is an improvement in technology which makes people lazy by door step delivery. There might also be brand delusions at times. However, virtual marketing can have security threats as confidential information's are shared.

Suggestions

The exhibitors of virtual marketing should be able to protect the confidential information secret with strong privacy. And the creation of advertisement in digital forms should be more

convincing to the customers by providing accurate facts of the products. It is also suggested that the business should take up new strategies on the matters of brand delusions. And Utmost care should be taken care off while delivering the products, mainly to sustain brand image. It is important for every business to look after their loyalty towards the customers.

Conclusion

The collaboration of traditional marketing and virtual marketing has its own pros and cons. Because of massive increase in the latest technology there is an ease to reach out to every customers and due to time constraints people find it better to get door step delivery. But comparatively majority of people do not prefer virtual marketing as they would be product defects, cannot be touched and felt, image shown and product delivered would be entirely different. But still majority of the people purchase products over virtual marketing in spite of all defects. It is mainly because of time constraints. At times some of customers buy products on occasions but prefer traditional marketing as it can be tested, verified and satisfies customers to some extent

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